

Kara Musa Pasha Mosque in Rethymno

also known as “Τζαμί Καρά Μουσά Πασά”, “Kara Moussa Pasha Mosque”, “Kara Musa Paşa Camii”

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Entry tags: Rethymno, Greece, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Greek, Aegean, Islam, Crete, Religious Place, Language, Turkic, Islamic Traditions, Sunni, Hanafi

Kara Musa Pasha, the Ottoman governor of Rethymno between 1670 and 1692, founded this mosque ca. 1683. Other structures within the mosque complex consist of a domed water fountain, which remains functional, and a domed mausoleum, now in a ruined state. The Kara Musa Pasha Mosque aligns with the qibla and follows a common Ottoman architectural mosque plan, consisting of a square building with a single dome, and a rectangular portico featuring three smaller domes. The mosque was financially supported by a vakf that consisted of the revenue from Amnatos and Perivolia. Following the population exchange between Greece and Turkey in 1923, the mosque was no longer used. After a period of abandonment, the mosque has undergone conservation: it was first restored between 1978 and 1980, and again from 2007 to 2008, with funding from the Third Community Support Framework.

Date Range: 1683 CE - 1923 CE

Region: Kara Musa Pasha Mosque

Region tags: Greece, Crete, Rethymno

Kara Musa Pasha Mosque in Rethymno with its associated türbe and fountain.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Giapitsoglou, Konstantinos, "Kara Musa Pasha Mosque," in *Ottoman Architecture in Greece*, 440-441.

– Source 1: Kolovos, Elias, "Monuments sans héritiers? Les édifices ottomans de Crète," *Anatoli*. 6 (6): 237-256.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://historicalcrete.ims.forth.gr/Toponyms/listing/kara-mousa-pasa>

– Source 1 Description: Kostas II. Papadakis, "Kara Moussa Pasha Mosque" in HistoricalCrete online map.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: A fountain is associated with the mosque.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: A wall and wrought iron fence with a gate separates the mosque enclosure from the surrounding area; although this wall likely does not date from the time of the mosque's founding in ca. 1683, it likely predates the abandonment of the mosque in 1924.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The mosque was located close to the edge of the Old Town of Rethymno, within the city walls.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: Kara Musa Pasha Mosque

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: Kara Musa Pasha Mosque

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Square

Notes: Kara Musa Pasha Mosque

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Individual

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: Abandonment

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: Partial conservation has been undertaken in the past 20 years (as of 2023) on the mosque and associated structures.

– Yes

Notes: Türbe associated with mosque.

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: Türbe associated with mosque

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Square

Notes: The türbe is square with a semi-circular dome

- ↳ One single feature
 - Other [specify]: N/A.
- ↳ A group of structures:
 - No
- ↳ A group of features:
 - No
- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - Yes
- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship
 - ↳ Worship:
 - Individual
- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes
 - ↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
 - Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

– Yes

Notes: Fountain associated with mosque.

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: Fountain associated with mosque

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Square

Notes: The fountain associated with the mosque is square with a semi-circular dome.

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:
– Individual

–Other [specify]: Water source

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– No

– Yes

Notes: Minaret of mosque

↳ A single structure
– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape
–Other [specify]: Octagonal

↳ One single feature
–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ A group of structures:
– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God (monotheistic)

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Private individual

– Other [specify]: Governor of Rethymno

Notes: The mosque was founded by Kara Musa Pasha in 1683. Kara Musa was the governor of Rethymno from 1670 to 1692.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

- Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

- Yes

Notes: The fountain is associated with a water source.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

- No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

- Yes

Notes: The mosque is the central structure and main point of focus.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

- No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

- Yes

↳ Earth

- No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Notes: There is a calligraphic plaque above the entrance containing information about the founding of the mosque.

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

Notes: The interior of the mosque is not currently accessible (as of 2023), meaning that interior decoration is not visible.

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Calligraphic plaque carved in relief

Notes: The calligraphic plaque above the entrance to the mosque is carved in relief.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: A türbe (mausoleum for 1 individual) is associated with the mosque.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Türbe (mausoleum)

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god (the monotheistic god of Islam) was worshipped at this place, but was not considered to be physically manifested ("present").

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god (the monotheistic god of Islam) was worshipped at this place, but was not considered to be physically manifested ("present").

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: N/A.

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god (the monotheistic god of Islam) was worshipped at this place, but was not considered to be physically manifested ("present").

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: N/A.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Answered prayer

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Answered prayer

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Angels and djinn might be considered to be present.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Angels and djinn might be considered to be present.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Humans communicated with non-human beings (angels) during prayer; however, prayer was directed to God (monotheistic), not to the angels.

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Humans communicated with non-human beings (angels) during prayer; however, prayer was directed to God (monotheistic), not to the angels.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 15-100

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Prayers occurred daily

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: While adult Muslim men were required/expected to attend congregational prayers in one of the city's mosques on Fridays, women could pray Friday prayers either in congregation or alone.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Notes: Worship at the mosque was a component of Eid ul-Adha and Eid ul-Fitr celebrations.

↳ Frequency of festivals

–specify: Major holidays (Eid ul-Adha and Eid ul-Fitr).

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

–Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Muslim members of the society participated in Eid ul-Adha and Eid ul-Fitr; Rethymno also had Jewish and Christian communities within its society.

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 50-100

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

Notes: Feasting for Eid ul-Adha and Eid ul-Fitr likely did not take place in the mosque itself, but was celebrated throughout the city, most often in people's homes.

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Non-elites

Notes: Food consumption was not limited to certain members of the population.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– No

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: The sheikh would have been male.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: The bureaucracy would have been associated with the management of the vakf endowed to this mosque.

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– No

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Yes

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Quran was read at this mosque.

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: The Quran was recited at this place.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– No

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: While religious specialists held an important role in interpreting scripture, individual worshippers likely had their own interpretations as well.

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Kara Musa Pasha Mosque in Rethymno, Kolovos, Elias. "Monuments Sans Héritiers? Les Édifices Ottomans De Crète, in *Anatoli 6*", 2015.

Reference: Kara Musa Pasha Mosque in Rethymno, Giapitsoglou, Konstantinos. "Kara Musa Pasha Mosque, in *Ottoman Architecture in Greece*". edited by Ersi Brouskari. Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008pp. 440-441. p.440-441